

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING BY CHANGING THE INITIAL VERSION OF TRAINING AIMED AT STUDENT ACTIVITY TO A NEW VERSION IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE REQUIREMENTS OF LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Akhadova Nilufar Fazliddin qizi

Teacher at the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Department of Uzbek
language and literature.

akhadovanilufar5@gmail.com

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Annotation

In this article, modern methods of teaching a foreign language, independent educational technologies have been successfully described from each. It allows students to customize any technology precisely in accordance with the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of teaching in a group of students.

Keywords: independent educational technology, method of communication, essay, essay - reasoning, discussion, dialogue, pedagogical system.

Аннотация

В этой статье были успешно описаны современные методы преподавания иностранного языка, самостоятельные образовательные технологии от каждого из них. Это позволяет студентам настраивать любую технологию точно в соответствии со структурой, функциями, содержанием, целями и задачами обучения в группе студентов.

Ключевые слова: самостоятельная образовательная технология, метод коммуникации, эссе, эссе - рассуждение, дискуссия, диалог, педагогическая система.

Introduction. language is the most important means of communication, without which the existence and development of human society is impossible. Today, the changes taking place in social relations, in the means of communication (the use of new information technologies) necessitate an increase in the communicative competence of students, improving their philological training, exchanging ideas in various situations in the process of interaction with them. other participants in communication, at the same time, are the correct use of the system of language and speech norms and the choice of adequate communicative behavior to the actual state of communication. In other words, the main goal of a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, that is, the ability to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language with native speakers. The upbringing aspect is an integral part of the educational process, therefore, all educational technologies provide for the upbringing of the necessary qualities of a mature person in students.

Materials and methods: modern educational technologies applied to the formation of communicative competence of a student in a foreign language are most effective for creating an educational environment that ensures the personality-oriented interaction of all participants in the educational process. It turns out that no matter how perfect the use of any teaching technology is, the ability to surface and develop students' abilities cannot create the most effective conditions for the creative search of the teacher.

The search for new pedagogical Technologies is due to the lack of positive motivation for

learning a foreign language in some students. Positive motivation is not enough, and sometimes not, because in learning a foreign language they have great difficulties and do not master the material due to their psychological characteristics.

The main purpose of the independent method of education is to give students the opportunity to independently acquire knowledge in the process of solving practical issues or problems that require the integration of knowledge in various fields of science. If we talk about this method as a pedagogical technology, then this technology implies a complex of research, research, problematic methods with a creative character. Inside, the role of project developer, coordinator, expert, consultant for the teacher is determined.

Results part. This technology develops the creativity of students, develops imagination and interests. In the process of preparing independent tasks, the creative and intellectual potential of students is revealed. The project method teaches to carry out research work, work in a team, conduct a discussion, solve problems. Life in modern society requires students to develop important cognitive abilities, such as developing their own thoughts, understanding experience, building a chain of evidence, accurately and reliably expressing their thoughts. The technology of developing independent thinking involves asking students questions and understanding the problem that needs to be solved. Critical thinking is of an individual independent nature, everyone creates their own ideas, forms their own assessments and beliefs independently of others, finds a solution to the problem itself and confirms it with reasonable, reasonable and reliable evidence.

Thinking is social because every thought is tested and shared with others. The active life position of the student is especially manifested in comparison of previously existing knowledge and concepts with newly acquired knowledge. There are various forms of work that ensure the development of independent thinking of students: essay, essay-reasoning, discussion, dialogue, role-playing, etc.

To develop intercultural communication skills, it is important to give students complete knowledge of the culture, customs and traditions of the English-speaking country so that students have an objective vision and can consciously choose their style of communication. Modeling situations of communication of cultures in English lessons allows students to compare the characteristics of the lifestyle of people in our country and in the countries of the studied language, help them better understand the culture of our country and develop the ability to express it. through English. This approach is possible only when real teaching tools are used.

Finding that information and communication technologies are increasingly used in the organization of the educational process, making it possible to effectively consider all possible aspects (from linguistics to cultural studies), improving the speech activity of a foreign language. Their use contributes to the improvement of language and intercultural competencies of students, the formation of a culture of communication in an electronic environment, the growth of Information Culture in general, as well as the development of computer skills: search, processing, transmission, systematization. presentation of the results of data and research activities by students.

The basis of interactive approaches is interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The main difference between independently performed exercises from simple ones is that they contain not only the material studied aimed not at strengthening, but at studying new ones.

Conclusion part: new independent education learning and strengthening of material (interactive lecture, visual aids, work with video and audio materials, "as a student teacher", "teaches everyone".

Under the discussion of complex and controversial issues and problems, creative tasks we understand such educational tasks that require students not just to repeat information, but creativity, since tasks contain more or less an element of uncertainty and, as a rule, have several approaches. The creative task is the content, the basis of any interactivity. A creative assignment (especially practical and close to student life) gives meaning to learning, motivates. The uncertainty of the answer and the ability to find your "right" solution based on your own special experience, and the experience of a colleague, friend allows you to create a basis for cooperation, joint education, communication of all participants.

Working in small groups is an integral part of many interactivity methods, such as mosaics, discussions, public hearings, almost all types of imitation, etc.

Make sure the students have the necessary knowledge and skills to complete the group assignment. The lack of knowledge will soon make itself felt - students will not try to complete the task. You should try to make your instructions as accurate as possible. It is unlikely that the group will be able to perceive more than one or two, even very specific, instructions at the same time, so the instructions should be written on the board or cards. Give the group enough time to complete the task.

When it comes to the practical application of technologies, it is absolutely not necessary to use one technology. The best way was to combine several educational technologies, combining the best of them.

Since we are engaged in the integration of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language in order to form an independent education of a student, it is necessary to carefully study the innovative ideas of modern Uzbek and foreign teachers for several years. To reveal the subjective experience of the student, to form educational methods of work that are personally significant for him, to educate moral ideals, to develop critical thinking,

it is concluded that this is a pedagogical system that helps to adequately assess and self-control.

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